

3,4-Coumarin-Pyrones: Part IV. Bromination of Coumarino-(3',4',5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrones and Synthesis of Coumarino-(3',4',4,5)-3-methyl-furans*

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Some coumarino(3',4',5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrones have been successfully brominated to give their 3-bromo derivatives. Coumarino(3',4',4,5)-3-methylfurans have been synthesised from these 3-bromo derivatives by treating them with ethanolic KOH and subsequent decarboxylation of the carboxylic acids obtained.

In our previous communications¹, synthesis of a number of coumarino(3',4',5,6)- α -pyrone derivatives has been reported. These substances can be expected to possess anti-coagulant activity on the basis of Chmielewska and Cieslaks²,³ hypothesis and this expectation is strengthened by the observation made by Arora and Mathur³ regarding the anti-coagulant activity of coumarino(3',4',5,6)-4-methyl- δ -phenyl- α -pyrone. On the basis of the same hypothesis coumarino(3',4',4,5)-furans can also be expected to possess anti-coagulant activity. Synthesis for these coumarino-furan derivatives is therefore developed from the now easily accessible coumarino(3',4',5,6)- α -pyrones¹, through their 3-bromo derivatives schematically shown below.

- (a) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 (b) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{Me}$
 (c) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{Me}$
 (d) $R_1 = \text{Et}, R_2 = \text{Me}, R_3 = \text{H}$.

- (e) $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 - R_3 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{---} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \right.$

*This forms part of the thesis of Jimmy Patell submitted to the University of Bombay in August 1965. Very recently a preliminary note on a similar work has been published by Dholakia and Trivedi, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1966, 160.

1. Patell and Usgaonkar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, 22, 406-7; this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 215-19; *ibid.*, 1966, 43, 536-46, 768-77.
 2. Chmielewska and Cieslak, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 135-46.
 3. Arora and Mathur, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1963, 20, 29-35.

Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4-methyl- α -pyrones (I) did not react with bromine readily, practically no reaction took place when the coumarino- α -pyrone (Ia) was treated with bromine in acetic acid using 1 mole of bromine (in 10% solution) per mole of the substance. At reflux temperature it took place to a slight extent but was not of any practical significance. Use of 2 moles of bromine per mole of the substance in the reaction had no marked improvement. Bromination, however, took place to give the 3-bromo derivative (IIa) when large excess of bromine (5 moles) in CS_2 solution (33%) was used in the reaction. The resulting crude product still contained a good amount of the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone (Ia). Using this method of bromination other coumarino-4-methyl- α -pyrones Ib, Ic, Id and benz (5', 6') coumarino-4-methyl- α -pyrone (Ie) were successfully brominated to give the corresponding 3-bromo derivatives IIb, IIc, IId and IIe respectively whose constitution follows from their reaction with ethanolic KOH discussed below. This observation is in agreement with that made in literature in the bromination of coumarins where the 3-bromo derivative is generally the first product obtained⁴. The formation of unstable 3, 4-dibromide is reported in few instances but it readily loses HBr to form the 3-bromo derivative^{4d}.

The 3-bromo derivative of the coumarino- α -pyrones (IIa-e) on treatment with ethanolic KOH got converted into the corresponding coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-2-carboxy-3-methylfurans IIIa, IIIb, IIIc, IIId and IIIe respectively (a property of 3-bromo derivatives of α -pyrones⁵). These coumarino-furan carboxylic acids (IIIa-e) were successfully decarboxylated by heating them in a metal bath at a temperature slightly higher than their m.p. to give nearly 80% yield of the corresponding coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3-methylfurans IVa, IVb, IVc, IVd, and benz (5', 6') coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3-methylfuran (IVe) respectively. This method of decarboxylation was found to be far superior than the conventional method of decarboxylation by heating the carboxylic acids with copper and quinoline. It gave a cleaner and purer product. Conversion of the 3-bromo derivative of coumarino- α -pyrone (II) into the corresponding coumarino-furan carboxylic acids (III) with ethanolic KOH, may be explained by the same mechanism as given by Dean⁶ for the conversion of 3-bromocoumarin to benzofuran carboxylic acid.

U. V. absorption spectra of coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3-methylfurans (IV) have been studied and their U.V. curves are recorded (Fig. 1). A sharp λ min at about 250-60 μ with two peaks at about 285-95 and 310-320 μ seems to be characteristic of these coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-furans.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4-methyl- α -pyrones (II): Bromine in CS_2 (20 ml, 33%) was added to a magnetically stirred suspension of the coumarino- α -pyrone (I) (3.0 g.) in CS_2 (10 ml.). After about 10 minutes, more bromine in CS_2 (10 ml, 35%) was added and

4. (a) Sethna and Shah, *Chem. Revs.*, 1945, **36**, 27; Dalvi and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1949, **26**, 359, 467; Elderfield, "Heterocyclic Compounds", Vol. II. John Wiley and Sons. p. 197.
- (b) Dean, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworth and Co., 1963, p. 180.
- (c) *ibid.*, p. 138.
- (d) Peters and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 830.
5. (a) Komppa, *Ber. dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1893, **26**, 2968.
- (b) Fittig and Ebert, *Annalen*, 1883, **216**, 162.

the stirring was continued for 7-8 hours. The reaction mixture was then left overnight exposed to air and allowed to get dried up. It was then mixed with water and the solid was filtered, it was washed well with water and weighed. It was crystallised from acetic acid. Repeated crystallisation gave pure product. Refer Table I.

FIG. 1

TABLE I

A. Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4-methyl- α -pyrones II.

Amount of I used in the reaction 3.0 g.

Coum- arino- α -pyrone.	Product and its Molecular Formula.	M. P. of the crude product and yield.	M. P. of pure product and shape of cryst.	Analysis			
				Found		Calculated	
				C	H	C	H.
Ia	Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4-methyl- α -pyrone (IIa) $C_{13}H_{17}O_4Br$	245-50 1.5 g.*	257-60 needles	52.0	2.6	50.9	2.3
Ib	Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4,6'-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb) $C_{14}H_{21}O_4Br$	237-50 4.0 g.	257-58 thin plates	52.2	3.0	52.3	2.81
Ic	Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4,8'-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIc) $C_{14}H_{19}O_4Br$	233-39 9.5 g.	238-40 plates	52.4	3.1	52.9	2.8
Id	Coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-3-bromo-4,6'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl- α -pyrone (IId) $C_{16}H_{23}O_4Br$	190-98 3.4 g.	200-02 needles	54.8	3.7	55.0	3.7
Ie	Benx (5', 6')-coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6,)-3-bromo-4-methyl- α -pyrone (IIe) $C_{17}H_{25}O_4Br$	220-23 3.4 g.	236-38 needles	57.4	2.6	57.1	2.5

*The compound could not be purified further. It always remained contaminated with little of the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone (Ia). M.P. and yield reported is after one crystallisation.

TABLE II

B. *Coumarino (3',4',4,5)-2-carboxy-3-methylfurans III.*

3-bromo der (II) and the amount used	Product and its Molecular Formula and yield.	M.P.	Analysis			
			Found C	H	Required H	
IIa 2.5 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-2-carboxy- -3-methyl furan (III a) $C_{13}H_8O_3$ 0.5 g	291-92 d needles	63.9	3.6	63.9	3.3
IIb 1.2 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-2-carboxy-3,6', dimethyl furan (IIb) $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ 0.32 g	265-66 d needles	64.9	4.3	65.1	3.9
IIc 2.0 g	Coumarino (3', 4', 5', 5,)-2- carboxy-3, 8'-dimethyl furan(IIIc) $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ 0.6 g.	282-84 d needles	65.1	4.0	65.1	3.9
II d 1.5 g	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-2-carboxy-3, 6'- dimethyl-8'-ethyl furan (IIId) $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ 0.48 g.	291-92 d	67.3	5.2	67.1	4.9
IIe 2.0 g.	Benz (5',6')-coumarino-(3',4',4,5)-2-carboxy 3-methyl furan (IIIe) $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$ 0.62 g.	274-75 d	69.3	3.4	69.4	3.4

TABLE III

C. *Coumarino (3',4',4,5)-3-methylfurans IV.*

Coumarino furan carboxy- lic acid and amt. used.	Product, its Molecular Formula and yield.	M.P. and shape of Cryst.	Analysis			
			Found C	H	Required C	H
III a 0.22 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3-methyl furan (IVa) $C_{12}H_8O_3$ 0.145 g.	155-56	71.6	3.6	72.0	4.0
III b 0.20 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3,6'-dimethyl furan (IVb) $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ 0.11g.	141-42 needles	72.7	4.3	72.9	4.6
IIIc 0.19 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3,8'-dimethyl furan (IVc) $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ 0.10 g.	133-34 needles	72.9	4.4	72.9	4.6
IIId 0.35 g.	Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-3,6'-dimethyl-8'- ethyl furan (IVd) $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ 0.17 g.	134-35 long needles	74.4	6.1	74.4	5.8
IIIe 0.30 g.	Benz (5',6') coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5) 3-methyl furan (IVe) $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$	216-17 needles	76.6	4.4	76.8	4.0

N. B. Product obtained after one crystallisation can be directly used for further reaction. It is normally contaminated with a little amount of the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone (I).

B. *Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-2-carboxy-3-methylfurans (III)*: The bromo derivative (II) (2.5 g.) was refluxed with ethanolic KOH (20 ml, 10%) for 4 hours. The solution was then

diluted with water and acidified. The precipitated solid was dissolved in aqueous NaHCO_3 and filtered off from a small amount of an insoluble residue*. It was reprecipitated by acidification and was crystallised generally from ethanol (Table II.)

C. *Coumarino (3', 4', 4, 5)-methylfurans (IV)*: The coumarino furan carboxylic acids(III) were decarboxylated by heating them (0.5 g.) in a glass tube at 300°C . in a metal bath. It melted, decomposed and the product sublimed. It was collected and crystallised from ethanol. (Table III.)

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*The insoluble residue is obtained if the bromo derivative used in the reaction is crude. This residue is the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone (I) from which the bromo derivative (II) is prepared. It is confirmed by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen.